

A REVIEW ON DATABASE SECURITY CHALLENGES IN CLOUD COMPUTING ENVIRONMENT

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ABSTRACT

Cloud computing is a system that offers many resources that may be customized, allowing for decentralized data management and storage. Cloud technologies have revolutionized concepts of data storage and access in organizations thus offering organizations flexible and efficient solutions. Cloud services such as DBaaS allows user to utilize sophisticated capabilities of databases without the responsibility of conventional databases. But with cloud computing, there is a great concern of security since issues such as data privacy, access control and compliance to regulatory requirements are paramount. This paper also explores the cloud computing architectural model, the differences between DBaaS and conventional cloud offerings, and the security risks of DBaaS. Much as it discusses the key areas of database security like data confidentiality, data integrity, and data availability, it provides information on security threats like the SQL injection or data breaches. Besides, it provides guidance on vulnerability management and incident handling in a context of cloud computing. To this end, this paper focuses on the conceptual clarification of the cloud database security best practices and the shared responsibility model between the providers and the users.

Keywords: Cloud computing (CC), Database as a Service (DBAAS), Database Security, Challenges,

Cite this Article: Sanjay Bauskar, (2024). A Review on Database Security Challenges in Cloud Computing Environment. International Journal of Computer Engineering and Technology (IJCET), 15(5), 842-852.

https://iaeme.com/MasterAdmin/Journal_uploads/IJCET/VOLUME_15_ISSUE_5/IJCET_15_05_077.pdf

I. INTRODUCTION

The ever-increasing need for cloud computing has led to a dramatic surge in interest in the concept over the last several decades. Several things could work in the favour of businesses who store their data on the cloud. CC has several benefits, such as less overhead expenses, easier IT management and infrastructure, and remote data access from almost anywhere with an Internet connection. CC refers to the method of delivering software applications and their supporting infrastructure over the Internet from a central data centre[1]. The cloud computing paradigm primarily encompasses three distinct deployment models: public, private, and hybrid clouds. The three primary types of cloud computing services are SaaS, IaaS, and PaaS. On top of that, a new variant known as database-as-a-service (DBaaS) has emerged; based on its specifications, it might fall into any of these main sorts [2].

Concerns about data security have significantly impacted cloud computing's adoption rate. Many individuals are horrified by the concept of entrusting another person's hard drive and CPU with their most important data and programs. Serious threats to an organization's software and data may be posed by security issues such as data loss, phishing, and botnets. In addition, the shared computing resources and multi-tenancy structure of CC have given rise to new security risks like Botcloud Attack, which calls for innovative solutions [3].

A special kind of database designed for usage in virtualised computer settings, or cloud environments, is called database as a service, or DBaaS. Large-scale data storage in the cloud is its main function. Given the variety of uses for cloud applications, DBaaS is becoming a feasible way to provide dependable and flexible data storage services to cloud applications[4]. Cloud-based IT solutions handle the problems of scalability, performance, availability, and affordability[5]. The following key contribution of as:

- To explore the fundamental components and architecture of CC, focusing on a roles of a front end and back end.
- To outline the primary security challenges associated with cloud computing, particularly in relation to database management, including data privacy and access control.
- To categorize and describe various attack vectors that threaten cloud databases, including passive and active attacks.
- To discuss effective strategies and best practices for mitigating security risks in cloud environments, such as encryption and access management.
- To emphasize the importance of understanding the shared responsibility model in cloud security, detailing the roles of both cloud providers and customers.

The following paper organized as: Section II and III provide the overview of cloud computing and Database As A Service (DBAAS), then Section IV provide the challenges of database securities, also Section V and VI give the literature review on this topic, and conclusion with future work.

II. OVERVIEW OF CLOUD COMPUTING

Cloud computing provides an alternative to the on-premises data center. When setting up an on-premises data center, we are in charge of every detail. This includes configuring the firewalls and networks, installing the operating system, setting up virtualization, acquiring and installing hardware, and configuring data storage. Following the completion of all setup, we assume responsible for its upkeep for the life of its existence [6]. As everyone is aware, cloud computing technology allows organizations of all sizes to store data in the cloud and retrieve it by using an internet connection from any location at any time. Figure 1 depicts cloud computing's architecture.

Figure 1: architecture of cloud computing

A combination of event-driven and service-oriented architectures make up cloud computing architecture [7]. There are two distinct components to cloud computing architecture:

- **Front End:** The front end is interfaced with by the client. Integration with cloud computing services may be facilitated by client-side APIs and apps. Internet browsers, thin and fat clients, mobile devices, tablets, and web servers make up what is called the front end.
- **Back End:** The back end is used by the service provider. In order to provide cloud computing services, it monitors all of the associated resources. It comprises a lot of things, such a lot of storage space for data, security features, virtual machines, models for deployment, servers, and ways to control traffic.

The user-friendly web interface offered by the cloud environment allows them to easily manage their network, storage, compute, and application resources.

a. Deployment and service models of Cloud Computing

There are two types of CC that shows in Figure 2[8].

Figure 2: Types of cloud computing models

- **Public Cloud:** The term "public cloud" refers to cloud resources that are under the ownership and management of a third party business. One may access a multitude of computer resources, such as servers, software, and storage, over the internet.
- **Private Cloud:** An individual firm or other organization might reserve the use of a group of cloud-based network resources called a private cloud. There are two possible locations for a private cloud: the company's own data centre and a different provider.
- **Hybrid Cloud:** Cloud computing is the practice of storing and processing data in both public and private clouds, with the two types of clouds linked together by technological means. Businesses benefit from hybrid cloud deployment choices because of the flexibility it offers.
- **Software as a Service (SaaS):** The term "software as a service" describes the model for delivering applications via the internet. The user never has to install the program on his computer; all he has to do is access it online.
- **Platform as a Service (PaaS):** PaaS gives consumers access to a development environment so they may install their own apps and code. Users are allowed to create their own applications that use the infrastructure of the provider. The application management capabilities may be obtained from the preset combination of operating system and application server offered by product as a service providers. Things like Ruby, J2EE, and LAMP (Linux, Apache, MySQL, and PHP) are a few examples.
- **Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS):** IaaS provides on-demand access to a broad range of computing resources, such as data storage, networks, operating systems, hardware, and storage devices. Infrastructure as a service customers may access the offerings over a WAN, or the internet [5]. The IaaS platform allows users to do things like construct virtual computers.
- **Database as a service (DBaaS):** As a Service (DBaaS) is an operational and architectural paradigm that enables IT suppliers to provide database functionality as a service to a larger number of customers.

b. Components of Cloud Computing

Here are the three main parts of CC: -

- **Client Computers:** Cloud computing allows users to engage with the service via client computers.
- **Distributed Servers:** The servers seem to be collaborating with each other while being dispersed over the several locations.
- **Data Centers:** The collection of servers is called a data centre.

III. OVERVIEW OF DATABASE AS A SERVICE (DBAAS)

The following resource kinds are commonly provided by cloud computing services, leading to a more widespread categorisation of cloud types: software, platforms, and infrastructure. Our primary emphasis in this study is the Daas service type. A good illustration of SaaS is DaaS. DBaaS is a cloud service that enables applications and is administered by a public or private cloud operator. It relieves the application team of the burden of handling standard database management tasks. Application developers shouldn't have to pay a DBA to manage the database or for them to be database professionals when using a DBaaS [7]. The Figure 3 displays a traditional database architecture.

Figure 3: Traditional database architecture

The provided Figure 3 depicts a typical architecture for DBaaS with a focus on high availability and performance. The application layer, represented by the topmost box, interacts with the application/analytcs servers through private or dedicated network connections. These servers, in turn, connect to the primary and secondary databases, which are configured in a Real Application Cluster (RAC) for redundancy and load balancing. This architecture ensures that the application can continue to function even if one of the database instances fails, providing a robust and scalable solution for various enterprise applications.

a. Database security

Today, an organization's success or failure is largely determined by its data, since most employ databases to store vital or significant organizational data. The data contains all credentials and sensitive information belonging to an organization, not simply user details alone. A large amount of money is spent by many organizations on database security, and since data is so vital, database security is crucial in both the public and commercial sectors. So, it is necessary to secure the data[9][10]. In today's information-centric environment, database security is essential to protecting sensitive data. Making sure databases are secure has grown crucial as businesses depend more and more on them to store and handle enormous amounts of data. Figure 4 illustrates the three primary components of database security.

Figure 4: Three main factors of Database Security

Three elements are essentially needed for data security: availability, integrity, and confidentiality.

- **Confidentiality** meaning that only authorized users may utilize the data,
- **Integrity** indicates that the data must be managed by a designated individual using a designated method, and

- **Availability** implies that the information must be accessible to authorized users at the proper time.

b. Attacks on Database

Database assaults are essentially divided into two categories [11]:

1. Passive Attacks

The observation is the main target of passive assaults. It is at this point that the attacker views the data in the database. Although more hazardous than active strikes, passive attacks provide less of a challenge.

- **Static Leakage:** Through this passive attack method, the perpetrator watches the database snapshot in order to extract values in plain text at a certain, predetermined moment. Data in the database is the only focus of static leakage, which only occurs at predetermined intervals and does not account for any changes to that data.
- **Linkage Leakage:** Passive attacks like this work by creating a connection between a value in the database and its index position; thereafter, the attacker can get the plain text value. In order to conduct a linkage leakage attack, one must first search the database index for the specific data that will be targeted.
- **Dynamic Leakage:** This passive attack style involves monitoring the database for a certain amount of time in order to create the plain text value.

2. Active Attacks

The fact that active attacks need changing data makes them more troublesome than passive ones.

- **Spoofing Attacks:** The cypher text is substituted with a newly produced value in this active attack.
- **Splicing Attacks:** There are two possible cypher text values in this active attack, and one of them gets swapped out for the other.
- **Replay:** The cypher text value is either destroyed or replaced with an older, previously updated version in this ongoing attack.

3. SQL Injection Attack

Injection of SQL instructions into SQL statements via web page input is a simple method by which malevolent people may compromise databases. There are many subtypes of SQL injection attacks, including:

- **Tautology Based Attacks:** Databases are a common target of tautology attacks due to their ease of execution. In this kind of attack, the perpetrator often goes through the authentication pages and gains access to the ones that aid execution by inserting SQL tokens into one or more conditional statements, making them always evaluate to true. For example, “SELECT name FROM bank WHERE name=’ ’ or 1=1--‘AND pin =’ ’.
- **Union Queries Based Attack:** When a tautology assault occurs, data recovery becomes impossible. In contrast, attackers committing union query-based attacks would inject data using unsafe parameters before merging the two queries using UNION. Therefore, this may access the database and obtain the data. For example, “SELECT name FROM bank WHERE name=’ ’ UNION SELECT name from employee WHERE employee id=’123’ -- AND pin=.
- **Piggybacked Queries:** One of the most damaging attacks, it works by inserting a new query into an existing one, much like the union query attack, but without changing the original query itself. For example, “SELECT name FROM bank WHERE name=’Preeti’ AND password =’abode’ AND pin=’132001’; drop table bank.

4. Data Encryption

This is the most fundamental and often used database security technique. This technique may be used to encrypt any kind of data or information such that its genuine content cannot be decoded by unauthorised individuals. Consequently, it offers security while sending encrypted communications from one person to another.

5. Data Scrambling

Data sanitisation, data masking, and data obfuscation are other names for data scrambling. This method is often used when a user has permission to access database data objects but yet wants to protect sensitive information from hackers. Such users include developers and members of testing teams. As a result, while critical data values are altered, they are still genuine.

IV. DATABASE SECURITY CHALLENGES IN CLOUD

There are some challenges of database security in cloud computing follow as[12][13]:

a. Data Privacy and Confidentiality

In cloud computing environments, ensuring data privacy and confidentiality is a significant challenge due to the multi-tenant nature of these systems. Multiple customers often share the same physical infrastructure, which raises concerns about potential data leakage or unauthorized access between tenants. To address this, it is important to implement robust data encryption mechanisms. Data should be encrypted both at rest and in transit. However, managing encryption keys and ensuring that data remains encrypted while being processed requires careful attention and can be complex.

b. Access Control

Effective access control is essential for database security in the cloud. Identity and Access Management (IAM) policies need to be meticulously configured to ensure that only authorized users have access to specific data. Misconfigurations can lead to excessive permissions, increasing the risk of unauthorized access or data breaches. Implementing Role-Based Access Control (RBAC) is also important but requires careful planning to avoid over-per missioning. Properly defining roles and permissions helps in reducing the risk of abuse or unauthorized data access.

c. Data Integrity

Maintaining data integrity is another critical challenge. It involves ensuring that data remains intact and unaltered by unauthorized parties. Implementing data validation and integrity checks can help in detecting any tampering or corruption. Additionally, secure backup and recovery processes are essential for protecting data integrity. Regular backups must be secured, and recovery processes should be tested to ensure they are effective against various types of attacks.

d. Compliance and Legal Issues

Compliance with regulatory requirements is often more complex in cloud environments. Regulations such as GDPR and HIPAA impose strict data protection and privacy standards, which can be challenging to adhere to, especially when data is stored across multiple jurisdictions. Data ownership and sovereignty also become critical issues, as organizations need to manage and ensure compliance with local laws regarding data storage and protection.

e. Vulnerability Management

Managing vulnerabilities in a cloud environment involves several challenges. Regular patch management is crucial to protect against known vulnerabilities; however, this responsibility can be shared between the cloud provider and the customer, potentially creating gaps. Additionally, addressing zero-day vulnerabilities—new and unknown threats that exploit weaknesses in the database software or cloud infrastructure—requires proactive measures and continuous monitoring.

f. Data Migration and Integration

Securely migrating data to and from the cloud presents its own set of risks. Ensuring that data transfers are secure and that the data remains intact during migration is vital. Integration of cloud databases with on-premises systems or other cloud services can also introduce security risks. Properly managing these integrations to ensure they do not compromise security is essential for maintaining a secure environment.

g. Incident Response and Monitoring

Effective incident response and monitoring are crucial for detecting and addressing security threats in real time. Cloud environments often require different approaches and tools compared to traditional setups. Implementing comprehensive logging and auditing mechanisms helps track access and changes, but managing and analyzing these logs can be complex. An effective incident response plan should be in place, tested regularly, and capable of handling various types of security incidents.

h. Provider Security Posture

The security of data in the cloud is partly dependent on the security measures implemented by the cloud provider. It is important to ensure that the provider follows industry best practices and has relevant security certifications. Understanding the shared responsibility model, where both the cloud provider and the customer have roles in securing the environment, is crucial for effective security management. Ensuring that both parties fulfill their respective roles is essential for maintaining a secure cloud infrastructure.

i. Cost Management

Balancing the cost of implementing robust security measures with budget constraints is another challenge. Effective cost management strategies are necessary to ensure that security measures are both effective and cost-efficient. Investing in security solutions should be balanced with the need to control operational expenses while ensuring that data and infrastructure are adequately protected.

In summary, addressing these database security challenges in cloud computing requires a combination of advanced technological solutions, effective policies, and ongoing vigilance. Businesses may improve data security and maintain a safe cloud environment by putting best practices into effect and keeping up to date on new threats.

V. LITERATURE REVIEW

This section provides a literature review on Database security challenges in CC Environment, summary shows in Table 1.

This, Singh, (2015) an explanation of cloud computing's definition, services offered, deployment method, characteristics, and difficulties is provided in this article. The primary focus of this paper is cloud computing database management. It also examines the features and difficulties of cloud DBMSs and contrasts different kinds of cloud databases[14].

This study, Li and Gao, (2015) focusses on the subject of mobile data services. The findings of previous research on mobile data services are first analyzed. Solutions for cloud-based mobile data services are then covered. The study concludes by looking at the problems and difficulties related to mobile data service in mobile cloud computing[15].

In this study, Munir, (2015) suggests a cloud DbaaS security approach. Anytime a person requests it, they may change their password. Security study also attains efficiency and validates the viability of the suggested DBaaS architecture. The cloud community will benefit from this by gaining insight into the most recent advancements in safe tactics, as well as any potential shortcomings and future directions[16].

In This research, Cinar, Guncer and Yazici, (2017) presents an improved version of our database security system, Info Fence, which is cloud-based and lightweight. It allows for the central management of several databases simultaneously. In our test environment, they were able to demonstrate that our suggested solution outperforms Oracle Audit Vault Server, a widely used product, when it comes to database security in a private cloud[17].

This, Dr. CH. V. Raghavendran, Dr. G. Naga Satish, Dr. P. Suresh Varma, (2016) As a result of technological advancements, a new system has emerged in the realm of computers, one that is service-oriented and offers several advantages. Cloud computing has enabled the IT sector to advance by one step. Huge, well-known companies have moved their processing and storage to the cloud. Describe cloud computing and its benefits in general terms in this article[18].

The "cloud" refers to this system of interconnected database servers[19]. By using cloud computing, organisations can easily adapt their server infrastructures to meet their evolving needs, effortlessly scaling up or down server capacity as needed. Provisioning, configuring, reconfiguring, and deprovisioning servers are all handled dynamically by a cloud computing platform. There are two types of servers that may be found in the cloud: physical and virtual. For more complex cloud computing, more hardware and software resources like storage area networks (SANs), firewalls, and network gear are usually included.

Table 1: Literature review summary for database security in cloud

Reference	Challenge	Methodology	Key Findings	Limitations	Future Work
[14]	Data Breaches	Literature review and case studies	Unauthorized access leads to significant data theft or loss; various strategies exist to mitigate these risks.	Focus on preventative measures may overlook detection and response strategies.	Develop more robust real-time monitoring systems.
[15]	Account Hijacking	Threat modeling and analysis of phishing attacks	Phishing remains a prevalent method for account hijacking, necessitating stronger user authentication methods.	User awareness is often insufficient to mitigate risks.	Develop user education programs alongside stronger security measures.
[16]	Insider Threats	Survey of existing frameworks and user behavior analysis	Insider threats are a significant risk; existing controls are often inadequate.	Difficulty in predicting malicious insider actions.	Implement more granular access controls and behavior analytics.
[17]	Insecure APIs	Security analysis of existing APIs	Vulnerabilities in APIs can expose databases to security risks; improved API security measures are essential.	Limited focus on third-party APIs.	Research stronger authentication and authorization mechanisms for APIs.
[18]	Compliance and Legal Issues	Regulatory framework analysis	Adhering to compliance standards is challenging; organizations struggle to manage data protection across different jurisdictions.	Compliance frameworks may not keep pace with evolving technology.	Propose dynamic compliance management tools for cloud environments.
[19]	Data Loss	Risk assessment and analysis of case incidents	Data loss incidents can result from various factors, including hardware failures and accidental deletions.	Not all scenarios for data loss are addressed.	Enhance backup and recovery strategies in cloud environments.

VI. CONCLUSION

Cloud computing is a common approach in the computing industry that allows for the processing of massive amounts of data using clusters of inexpensive machines. Due to the centralized nature of the shared hardware, software, and other data made available by the cloud, the DBase-related service delivery by cloud service providers is crucial. This article presents Database/Relational Cloud, a novel DBaaS for transactional purposes. In conclusion, while cloud computing, particularly through models like DBaaS, offers substantial benefits according to accessibility, scalability, and cost-efficiency, it also presents multifaceted security challenges that organizations must address to protect sensitive data. Effective strategies must be implemented to ensure privacy, maintain data integrity, and adhere to compliance requirements. The security landscape in cloud environments necessitates a proactive approach to vulnerability management, incident response, and continuous monitoring. Organizations must engage in collaborative security practices with cloud providers, recognizing the shared responsibility model to enhance their security posture. By adopting comprehensive policies, leveraging advanced technologies, and fostering a culture of security awareness, organizations can effectively mitigate risks and secure their data in the cloud.

Future work should focus on developing enhanced security protocols tailored for cloud databases, utilizing machine learning to improve anomaly detection and predict breaches. Additionally, researching innovative encryption techniques and data privacy solutions is crucial to maintaining confidentiality and integrity without sacrificing performance. Exploring hybrid security models that integrate traditional and cloud-native measures can address unique challenges in multi-cloud environments. Lastly, implementing comprehensive training programs will help organizations raise awareness of cloud security challenges and best practices for data protection and compliance.

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Citation: Sanjay Bauskar, (2024). A Review on Database Security Challenges in Cloud Computing Environment. *International Journal of Computer Engineering and Technology (IJCET)*, 15(5), 842-852.

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